

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B368
 Date: 10 May 2008
 Take Off: 08:07:32Z
 Landing: 12:59:19Z
 Flight Time 4h 51m

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Baltic Sea, Finland, Sweden

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Latti Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	y
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Y/n/y/n/n
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / TDLAS / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	FAAM	
13	Mission Scientist 2	Claire McConnell	University of Reading	
14	CPI rack 2	Ian Crawford	University of Manchester	
15	Mission Scientist 3	Radek Krejci	University of Stockholm	
16	Mission Scientist 4	Maria Frontosa	University of Leeds	

Flight Track:

B368 Track 10-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B368
 Date: 10 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: Baltic Sea, Sweden, Finland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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063221		Start-Up	1.8 kft	359	48'04.68N,11'17.51E
075612		ASP	1.8 kft	359	Open
075836	080128	Pirouette 1	1.8 kft	359	Start 355 deg, right
080732		T/O	3.0 kft	359	Oberpfaffenhofen
080954		Event	5.1 kft	359	Zero JW & Nevz
081703		Video	17.3 kft	359	Start FFC & RFC
083019		Event	24.0 kft	359	Open LBBR shutter
094539		Video	24.0 kft	359	Change Tapes
095843	101237	Profile 1	14.8 - 2.1 kft	359	End at B8, 2.3k'
101238	104601	Run 1	2.1 kft	359	Start at B8, 2.3k'
102451		Event	2.1 kft	359	Heimann Cal
102639		Event	2.1 kft	359	QNH 1021hPa
102902		Waypoint	2.1 kft	359	B6
103247		Turn	2.1 kft	359	for ATC
104216		Waypoint	2.1 kft	359	Abeam B5, 4m South
104602	105440	Profile 2.1	2.1 - 8.0 kft	359	From 2.3k'
105441	110230	Run 2	8.0 kft	359	2.3k'
110230	110518	Profile 3	8.0 - 7.0 kft	359	
110519	111140	Run 3	7.0 kft	359	Q1020
111140	111319	Profile 4	7.0 - 6.5 kft	359	2.3k', Interrupt
111320	112042	Run 4	6.5 kft	359	Gliders below
111700		Video	6.5 kft	359	Change Tapes
112043	112906	Profile 4	6.5 - 2.5 kft	359	Gliders below 2.7k'
112553		Event	4.3 kft	359	Expedite to 2.7k'
112907	114610	Run 5	2.5 kft	359	2.7k'
113631		Waypoint	2.6 kft	359	Abeam A31/B2
114055		Waypoint	2.5 kft	359	A30
114610	115131	Profile 5	2.5 - 8.0 kft	359	From 2.7k'
115131	120119	Profile 6	8.0 - 2.1 kft	359	End at 2.3k'
115535		Deviate	5.7 kft	359	ATC request
115930		Event	3.1 kft	359	Rturnn to track
120120	121205	Run 6	2.1 - 1.9 kft	359	2.3k'-2k'
120158		Descend	2.1 kft	359	To 2k'for ATC
120247		Waypoint	1.8 kft	359	A29
120428		Event	1.9 kft	359	Plume
120900		Waypoint	1.9 kft	359	A28
121028		Event	1.9 kft	359	Heimann Cal
121205	121435	Profile 7	1.9 - 3.3 kft	359	2k'-3.5k'
121436	122421	Run 7	3.3 kft	359	3.5k'
122422	123111	Profile 8	3.3 - 11.9 kft	359	From 3.k'
123111	124255	Profile 9	11.9 - 3.3 kft	359	To 3.5k', Q1021
123337		Event	9.8 kft	359	Zero JW & Nevz
124012		Waypoint	5.3 kft	359	A27
124255	124945	Run 8	3.3 kft	359	3.5k', Q1021
125919		Land	-.20 kft	359	Riga, Latvia
130115	130351	Pirouette 2	-.20 kft	359	Start 330, right turn
130825		ASP	-.20 kft	359	Close
130845		Shutdown	-.20 kft	359	56'55.48N, 23'58.68E

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B368 Track 10-MAY-08

EUCAARI Flight B368
FAAM sortie brief

Saturday 10th May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight) – Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight) – Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM (Directflight) – Dawn Quinn
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. CCN –
7. AMS – Paul Williams
8. Cloud Physics –
9. SP2 – Dantong Liu
10. CAPS? – Ian Crawford?
11. SWS/SHIMS – Debbie O’Sullivan
12. Wet Neph – James Bowles
13. Mission Scientist – Keith Bower
14. Mission Scientist – Claire McConnell
15. Mission Scientist Training - Maria Frontoso
16. Guest – Radek Krejci

Other comments:

Power on at: 0400Z

Take off: 0800Z

Landing at Riga: 1230Z

Operating Area:

Baltic Sea, Finland, Sweden and landing to refuel in Riga (Latvia).

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of aged re-circulated pollution centred over the Baltic Sea.

Weather

Forecast predicts high pressure centred over southern Sweden with very weak flow.
Clear skies preferred.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies and no delays prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway.
(360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Oberpfaffenhofen at 0800z (1000 local)
3. Climb to high altitude (FL250) and transit to way point B8
[2h 5mins, T=2h 5]
4. Profile descent to 2600ft to way point B7
[10 mins, T=2h 15]
5. Follow the route: B7-B6-B5-B4-B3-B2-B1/A30-A29-A28-A27 along SLR at
MPA during route. Possible sawtooth profiles along route, locations to be
determined during flight.
[2h 15 mins, T=4h 30]
6. SLR from A27 to Riga at 2kft and profile to landing at Riga.
[30 mins, T=5h]
7. If a pirouette was performed before take off and sky is clear at Riga, perform
pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B368

Date: 10/05/08	Operator: pdr	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +1	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:51:45	320	0.09		5												Fl 60	
10:53:13	300	0.09		5												Fl 70	
10:54:50	200	0.09		5												End profile 2 start run 2 at fl80	
10:57:00	100	0.09		0													
10:59:00	200	0.09		0													
11:01:00	200	0.1		1													
11:02:30	250	0.1		2												End run 2 start profile 3	
11:05:19	400	0.09		2												End profile 3 start run 3	
11:07:00	500	0.1		5													
11:09:00	450	0.1		5													
11:11:00	450	0.1	597	5													
11:11:40	470	0.1		5												End run 3 start profile 4	
11:13:20	660	0.1		5												End profile 4 start run 4 at Fl65	
11:15:00	500	0.1		5													
11:17:00	450	0.1		5													
11:19:00	50	0.09															
11:20:40	80	0.1		2												End run 4 continue profile 4	
11:21:48	100	0.1	598	2												Fl 60	
11:24:30	100	0.09		0												Fl50	
11:26:19	450	0.09		1												Fl40	
10:28:00	250	0.1		1												Fl30	
11:29:10	230	0.09		2												End profile 4 Fl25 stat run 5	
11:31:00	200	0.09		2													
11:33:00	180	0.1		1													
11:35:00	250	0.1		0													
11:37:00	340	0.09		0													
11:39:00	280	0.09		1													
11:41:00	350			1													
11:43:00	450	0.09		1													
11:45:00	500	0.09		1													
11:46:11	400	0.09		1												End run 5 start profile 5	
11:47:45	380	0.1		2												Fl 40	
11:48:45	50	0.09		1												Fl 50	
11:49:44	25	0.12		0												Fl 60	
11:50:45	25	0.13		0												Fl 70	
11:51:30	25	0.07		0												Fl 80 end profile 5 start profile 6	
11:53:15	50	0.08		0												Fl 70	
11:54:55	40	0.09		0												Fl 60	
11:57:00	300	0.09		0												Fl 50	
11:58:10	500	0.1	599	1												Fl 40	
11:59:38	470	0.1		1												Fl 30	
12:01:20	540	0.1		1												Fl 21 end profile 6 stat run 6	
12:03:00	250	0.09		1													

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.6	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.6	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.05	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.67		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -0.85	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -2.85		

B368_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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06:08:03.17 --- - - -
06:08:03.18 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:08:03.19 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:08:03.19 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B368
06:08:03.19 --- - - -
06:08:09.30 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:08:12.46 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
06:08:13.03 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
06:08:25.92 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:08:26.01 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:08:26.10 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:09:10.82 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:09:13.06 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:09:14.90 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:09:16.46 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:09:17.89 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:09:17.90 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:09:19.25 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:09:21.54 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:09:21.55 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:09:27.42 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:10:58.00 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:10:58.01 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:10:59.89 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:10:59.89 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:10:59.91 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:16:00.96 USH - - - Idling
06:16:00.97 SWS - - - Idling
06:16:01.49 LSH - - - Idling
06:33:10.05 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:10.06 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:10.06 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:14.54 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:33:19.56 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:19.65 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:20.00 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:20.51 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:20.72 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:26.46 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:28.80 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:28.93 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:29.15 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:29.81 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:29.95 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:35.64 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:57.87 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:57.89 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:58.33 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:33:58.81 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:33:59.03 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:34:04.76 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:42:39.56 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:42:39.61 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:42:39.85 USH - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:42:39.94 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:42:40.53 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:42:40.74 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:42:43.69 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:42:43.96 LSH - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:42:46.46 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:42:51.45 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:42:56.26 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
06:42:57.30 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:42:58.50 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
06:42:58.78 USH - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:42:59.45 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.

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06:43:02.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:05.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:05.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:43:06.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:08.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:11.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:43:15.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:15.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:43:16.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:17.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:18.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:48.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:48.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:43:49.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:52.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:52.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:43:53.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:43:55.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:43:56.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:43:56.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:01.50	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:44:04.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:44:08.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:44:13.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:13.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:44:14.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:15.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:16.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:17.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:18.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:19.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:20.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:21.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:21.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:44:22.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:23.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:27.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:28.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:44:28.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:30.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:49:00.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
06:51:36.15	---	-	-	-	-	
06:51:36.15	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:51:36.15	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment	+++					
06:51:36.15	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B368
06:51:36.15	---	-	-	-	-	
06:51:50.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
06:51:55.05	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
06:52:06.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:52:06.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:52:06.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:53:32.54	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:53:33.92	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:53:33.93	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:53:35.54	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:53:37.19	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:53:38.74	USH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
06:53:38.75	USH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
06:53:41.05	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
06:53:41.05	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
06:53:43.27	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:53:44.26	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:53:45.56	LSH	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 25ms.
06:53:45.56	LSH	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 25ms.
06:53:48.02	LSH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 30ms.
06:53:48.02	LSH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 30ms.
06:53:49.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:53:49.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

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06:53:49.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:16.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:16.59 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
06:54:17.00 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:18.47 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:19.12 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:20.09 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:54:23.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:24.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:25.75 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:26.39 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:28.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:29.46 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:30.38 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:54:31.13 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:54:34.74 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:58:39.73 --- - - - -
06:58:39.73 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:58:39.73 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:58:39.73 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B368
06:58:39.73 --- - - - -
06:58:53.52 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:58:55.59 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
07:03:37.74 --- - - - -
07:03:37.75 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:03:37.75 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:03:37.75 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B368
07:03:37.75 --- - - - -
07:03:45.94 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:03:49.73 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:03:57.89 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:03:58.98 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:04:00.59 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:04:00.69 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:04:00.77 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:04:01.04 SWS - - 10 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:01.05 SWS - - - 10 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:15.60 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:04:16.58 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:04:17.71 USH - - 10 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:17.71 USH - - - 10 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:19.10 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:04:20.54 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:04:21.84 LSH - - 10 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:21.84 LSH - - - 10 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
07:04:28.93 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:28.93 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:28.94 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:33.88 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 600ms.
07:04:33.89 LSH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 600ms.
07:04:37.63 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
07:04:37.63 USH - - - 50 - - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
07:04:40.79 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
07:04:40.80 SWS - - - 50 - - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
07:04:43.88 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:04:47.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:47.37 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:47.60 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:48.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:48.50 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:54.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:05:06.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:05:06.81 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:05:06.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:05:07.73 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:05:07.96 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:05:13.71 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

07:07:15.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:15.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:15.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:07:15.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:15.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:07:16.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:16.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:16.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:07:19.93	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:07:21.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:24.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:25.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:25.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:26.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:27.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:31.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:32.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:32.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:33.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:34.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:07:36.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:07:42.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:09.27	---	-	-	-	-	***
07:08:09.87	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
07:08:12.08	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:08:14.01	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:08:15.68	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:08:23.77	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:08:27.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:08:27.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:08:27.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:08:27.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:28.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:33.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:06.38	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:09:11.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:11.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:11.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:11.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:12.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:17.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:11:58.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
07:12:00.40	SWS	170.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:12:06.90	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:12:08.57	SWS	-1.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:25:27.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:25:30.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:30.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:30.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:31.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:31.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:37.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:39.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:40.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:40.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:41.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:41.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:46.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:26:25.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:26:25.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:26:25.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:26:26.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:26:26.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:26:32.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:27:49.99	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:27:54.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:27:54.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:27:54.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:27:55.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

07:27:55.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:01.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:02.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:02.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:03.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:03.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:04.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:09.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:38.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:45:43.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:43.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:43.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:44.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:44.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:50.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:02.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:02.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:02.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:03.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:03.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:08.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:47:41.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2 deg
07:51:36.38	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
07:51:37.38	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:51:37.70	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
07:51:38.04	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
07:51:38.37	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
07:51:38.69	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
07:51:39.00	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
07:51:39.48	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
07:51:40.96	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
07:51:41.27	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
07:51:41.79	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
07:51:42.76	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
07:51:43.16	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -0.500
07:51:46.95	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:51:51.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:51.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:51.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:51:52.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:52.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:51:58.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:30.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:30.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:30.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:52:31.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:31.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:52:37.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:58:19.89	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
07:58:39.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** piroeuute 1 355 deg start right turn
08:01:30.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p 1
08:01:42.38	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:01:46.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:46.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:46.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:47.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:47.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:50.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:50.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:51.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:51.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:53.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:16.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:09:21.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:21.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:21.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:22.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:22.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:28.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

08:09:40.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:40.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:09:40.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:41.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:09:46.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:13:12.71	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
08:13:16.42	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
08:14:15.35	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.000
08:14:17.93	SWS	-1.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
08:14:18.27	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
08:14:19.12	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
08:14:19.42	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
08:14:19.83	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
08:14:20.73	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
08:14:21.15	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
08:14:22.02	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
08:14:22.55	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
08:14:25.12	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:28:39.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
08:28:40.04	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
08:28:44.69	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:28:50.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:50.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:50.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:51.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:51.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:57.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:01.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:29:01.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:29:01.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:29:03.54	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.000
08:29:05.23	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:29:06.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:06.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:06.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:10.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:10.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:11.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:12.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:17.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:17.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:17.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:17.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:18.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:18.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:31:36.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:32:33.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2 still
08:41:12.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:41:16.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:41:16.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:41:16.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:41:17.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:41:17.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:41:23.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:48:27.26	SWS	175.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
08:48:28.97	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:48:42.80	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
08:48:44.97	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 46.000
08:48:48.22	SWS	46.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.500
08:48:49.15	SWS	45.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
08:48:56.20	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 55.000
08:49:04.97	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
08:49:17.04	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.000
08:49:18.77	SWS	175.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:49:21.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:21.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:21.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

08:49:22.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:23.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:28.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:39.30	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:11:44.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:44.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:44.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:45.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:45.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:49.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:49.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:50.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:50.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:50.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:07.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
09:23:26.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
09:25:29.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
09:42:23.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
09:45:53.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
09:51:58.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
09:57:53.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3 deg
09:58:56.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 1
09:59:40.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
10:12:39.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint B8, end of profile 1 and start of run 1
10:18:28.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:28.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:28.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:30.51	SWS	175.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
10:18:32.30	SWS	-4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:18:33.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:33.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:33.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:37.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:18:42.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:42.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:42.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:43.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:43.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:49.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:52.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:52.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:53.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:53.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:58.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:40.98	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
10:20:41.00	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
10:20:42.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:43.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:44.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:45.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:47.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:48.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:00.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:25:05.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:05.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:05.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:06.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:07.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:12.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:14.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:14.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:14.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:15.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:15.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:21.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:06.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** b6
10:29:11.17	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.

10:29:16.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:16.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:16.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:17.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:22.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:03.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1 start of sawtooth profile ascent
10:46:11.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing to 5500 ft
10:48:14.83	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:48:20.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:20.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:20.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:21.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:21.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:26.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:29.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:29.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:29.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:30.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:30.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:35.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:47.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run
11:02:34.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:02:42.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
11:04:56.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run at F
11:05:00.48	---	-	-	-	-	***
11:05:19.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** fl 700 now
11:10:18.86	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:10:23.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:23.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:23.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:24.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:24.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:30.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:31.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:31.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:31.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:31.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:32.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:35.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:11:51.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile descent down to 2300 ft
11:13:23.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
11:13:44.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** (end of profile 4 start of 4 at FL 65)
11:20:39.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1
11:20:43.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of decent
11:20:59.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 4 profile decent recoming p 4
11:24:46.06	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
11:25:07.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
11:27:30.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
11:29:08.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run
11:29:32.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5 2700 ft
11:30:52.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
11:38:23.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** A31/B2 one of the supersites
11:38:30.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at minus 1
11:40:54.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** a 30
11:44:30.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
11:46:11.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:46:22.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile climb to FL 800
11:46:29.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL 80
11:51:31.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8000 now back down to 2300 ft
11:52:51.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3
12:01:35.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p6 strat of run 6
12:12:08.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of p climb
12:14:37.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at 3500 ft
12:24:23.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of climb
12:24:40.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** sawtooth ascent profile 8 to FL 120
12:30:03.66	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.

12:30:03.67	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
12:30:05.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:30:07.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:08.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:30:09.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:13.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of pr
12:31:19.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** now decending
12:32:41.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:42:56.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile start of run at 3500 ft
12:44:06.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3 still
13:00:33.67	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:00:37.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:00:37.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:00:37.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:00:38.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:38.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:38.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:45.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2 deg
13:00:51.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:00:53.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:19.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** piroeutte 2 heading of 330
13:03:53.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of pirouette 2

Flight:

B368

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS)

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B368

Date: 10 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not run
2. Digital Video Box – stickle brick no longer holding it up, now resting on keyboard at aft CorCon
3. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.
4. Digital Video – DFC not recording. Restarted Streaming Activator at 0941, then okay.
5. HORACE Displays – FM Flight Summary window “lost network connection” occasionally, suspect due to number of windows open.

Instrument Status roundup

SWS - Okay

Cloud Physics – 2DP noisy, PCASP needs cleaned before Mondays flight

SP2 –Okay

CAPS/CPI /2DS – CAPS Heaters appears to be generating noise which is affecting the instrument signals. CAS side doesn't work, SIP okay, 2DS not run.

Neph/PSAP/Filters/CVI – Wet neph pc rebooted at 1024Z and again at 1039Z, online @1052Z.

Comms problems with Chiller Unit.

Filters, no increase in counts on Elec unit when pump switched on. 2 sets of filters tried with same results. Remove filter packs and switch pump on, works okay.

AMS – Blew a fuse on pre-flight so didn't finish pumping down by t/o time.

SMPS not seeing anything at FL80, fine at low level

CCN – Okay

PAN/ Core Chem - Okay

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 10.05.08

Flight No: B 368

Pre-Flighter: STEVE CONNOR.

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	NIU
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☒	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	NIU
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☒	INU	Navigate then back to Align	NIU
24	☐			
25	☒	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	☒	CGPS	Set up	NIU
29	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	☒	All other covers	Removed	
41	☒	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N Hangar
42	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
	☐			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
	☐	ICEX applied		
	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B368:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by
Mission Scientist	yet to be scanned by Keith Bower
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created – Keith Bower
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
CCN	Operator does not create a log sheet
PAN	Operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log as CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b368_094104_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b368_104104_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b368_114104_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b368_124104_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b368_134104_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_075640_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_075656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_085656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_094056_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_104056_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_114056_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_124056_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b368_134056_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_075705_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_085705_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_094059_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_104059_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_114059_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_124059_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b368_134059_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_075708_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_085708_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_094101_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_104101_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_114101_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_124101_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b368_134101_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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